

ISic3070

I.Sicily inscription 3070

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone; stucco

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Marsala

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331223

1. Ἀχιλλεὺς Προθύμου,
2. χάρει καὶ κατὰ
3. χθονός.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284813

EDCS 59700188

PHI 331223

Bibliography

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